

Penta- and Hexacoordinated Aluminium(III) Complexes of Thiosemicarbazones

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Manuscript received 13 October 1992, revised 22 February 1993, accepted 30 April 1993

Thiosemicarbazones and their metal complexes show a wide spectrum of medicinal properties¹. Such activities are often related to complexing ability of these ligands with the metal ions. A plethora of literature is available on the complexes of these ligands with transition and non-transition metals², but no such work has been reported on the aluminium(III) complexes with these ligands. In view of this, it was considered of interest to synthesise the complexes derived from aluminium(III) isopropoxide with thiosemicarbazones of heterocyclic ketones.

Results and Discussion

Analytical and physical data of the thiosemicarbazones (Table 1), the aluminium complexes (Table 2) and t-butoxyaluminium complexes (Table 3) are presented.

The elemental analyses of the complexes (Table 2) indicate 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 (M : L) stoichiometries. The complexes are coloured solids and soluble in organic solvents. The molecular weights of these complexes indicate the dimeric nature of the mono- and bis-alkoxy derivatives and the monomeric nature of tris-ligand metal complexes. The dimerisation in these complexes was considered to involve isopropoxy bridges³.

The thiosemicarbazones display two sharp ir bands around 3 450 and 3 350 cm⁻¹ assignable⁴ to ν_{asym} and ν_{sym} NH₂ respectively, which did not alter in the metal complexes, indicating their non-involvement in coordination. A medium intensity band appearing at 3 120–3 200 cm⁻¹ (NH) in the ligands, disappears in the metal complexes, indicating the possible deprotonation on the β -nitrogen after complexation with metal ion⁵. The band at ~ 1 035 cm⁻¹ (C=S) for the free ligand disappears in the metal complexes, indicating the coordination of

the ligands through the sulphur atom⁶. The band at 1 590 \pm 10 cm⁻¹ (C=N) of the free ligand shifts to higher wave number in the metal complexes, suggesting the coordination through the azomethine

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THIOSEMICARBAZONES

Ligand	M.p. (°C)	Analyses % : Found/Calcd.)	
		N	S
2-Acetylfuran thiosemicarbazone (AcFur.TSCZH)	165 (Yellow)	22.38 (22.93)	17.92 (17.49)
2-Acetylthiophene thiosemicarbazone (AcThiop.TSCZH)	155 (Light yellow)	20.43 (21.08)	33.00 (32.17)
2-Acetylpyridine thiosemicarbazone (AcPyd.TSCZH)	142 (Light yellow)	27.97 (28.83)	16.93 (16.50)
2-Acetylnaphthalene thiosemicarbazone (AcNaph.TSCZH)	144 (White)	16.88 (17.26)	12.56 (13.17)

nitrogen to the metal atom⁷. The ir spectra of the 1 : 1 complexes show new bands at 1 170–950 and 960–900 cm⁻¹, which may be attributed to ν C–O vibrations of the terminal and bridging isopropoxy groups respectively, while the 1 : 2 complexes show the bands only at 960–900 cm⁻¹, which may be attributed to bridging isopropoxy groups. The complexes exhibit new bands at 590–460 and 410–300 cm⁻¹ which may be attributed to the different vibrational modes of Al←N⁹ and Al–S⁹, respectively.

The ¹H nmr spectra of the ligand 2-acetylthiophene thiosemicarbazone, and its 1 : 1 aluminium(III) reveal the following. The disappearance of the NH resonance signal of the ligand from δ 10.68 in the aluminium(III) complex, indicates the depro-

nation of the functional group during the complexation. The methyl protons signal ($H_3C-C=N$) appearing at δ 1.68 in the ligand undergoes deshielding (δ 2.56) in case of the aluminium(III) complex, confirming the coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the central metal atom. The spectrum of complex shows two doublets at δ 0.72 (J 7.2 Hz) and 0.76 (J 7.2 Hz) which are ascribable to *gem*-dimethyl protons of the terminal and bridging isopropoxy groups respectively. The 1 : 1 aluminium(III) complex also shows two septets at δ 4.18 (J 7.2 Hz) and 4.24 (J 7.2 Hz) due to methine proton of terminal and bridging isopropoxy groups respectively. These isopropoxy signals disappear in the spectra of *t*-butoxy derivatives of aluminium(III) and new signals appear at δ 0.64 and 0.72 due to the methyl protons of terminal and bridging *t*-butoxy groups, which clearly indicates the replacement of isopropoxy groups by *t*-butoxy groups in the exchange product. The azomethine methyl protons signals in the *t*-butoxy complex appears at δ 2.48.

The ^{13}C nmr spectra of 2-acetylthiophene thiosemicarbazone and its 1 : 1 aluminium(III) reveal the following. The main feature of the spectra are the reasonable shifting of the thiolic carbon from δ 179.78 to 169.13 ppm and azomethine carbon from δ 146.20 to 142.39 ppm in the metal complex, which further confirms the coordination of sulphur and nitrogen to the central metal atom. The spectrum of the 1 : 1 complex shows new signals at δ 23.28, 23.90 ppm (β -carbons) and 73.07, 75.24 ppm (α -carbons) which are ascribable to terminal and bridging isopropoxy groups respectively. The presence of two types of isopropoxy groups confirms the pentacoordinated environment for aluminium in the 1 : 1 complex.

On the basis of the above discussion a pentacoordinated structure for the 1 : 1 and a hexacoordinated structure for the 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 aluminium(III) complexes are suggested.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF ALUMINIUM(III) COMPLEXES

Reactants			Decomp. temp. (°C)/ (Colour)	Analysis Pr ⁱ OH (g)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)*		
Al compd. (g)	Ligand (g)	Molar ratio			Al	N	S
Al(OPr ⁱ) ₃ O (1.06)	AcFur.TSCZH (0.96)	1 : 1	176 (Dark yellow)	0.30 (0.30)	8.46 8.24	12.48 12.83	10.05 9.79
Al(OPr ⁱ) ₃ (0.69)	AcFur.TSCZH (1.24)	1 : 2	200 (Yellow)	0.38 (0.39)	6.26 5.98	18.08 18.65	14.58 14.23
Al(OPr ⁱ) ₃ (0.41)	AcFur.TSCZH (1.10)	1 : 3	146 (Dark yellow)	0.36 (0.36)	4.86 4.70	21.23 21.97	16.99 16.76
Al(OPr ⁱ) ₃ (1.28)	AcThiop.TSCZH (1.26)	1 : 1	106 (Yellow)	0.35 (0.36)	7.98 7.85	12.05 12.23	18.12 18.67
Al(OPr ⁱ) ₃ (0.62)	AcThiop.TSCZH (1.22)	1 : 2	210 (Dark yellow)	0.36 (0.36)	5.72 5.59	16.85 17.41	27.25 26.57
Al(OPr ⁱ) ₃ (0.41)	AcThiop.TSCZH (1.19)	1 : 3	120 (Yellow)	0.36 (0.35)	4.46 4.33	19.58 20.27	31.78 30.93
Al(OPr ⁱ) ₃ (1.23)	AcPyd.TSCZH (1.17)	1 : 1	220 (Yellowish brown)	0.33 (0.34)	7.74 7.97	16.17 16.55	9.95 9.47
Al(OPr ⁱ) ₃ (0.65)	AcPyd.TSCZH (1.23)	1 : 2	176 (Brown)	0.35 (0.37)	5.53 5.70	22.96 23.70	13.92 13.56
Al(OPr ⁱ) ₃ (0.45)	AcPyd.TSCZH (1.28)	1 : 3	158 (Dark brown)	0.37 (0.38)	4.58 4.44	26.88 27.69	16.54 15.85
Al(OPr ⁱ) ₃ (0.91)	AcNaph.TSCZH (1.09)	1 : 1	330 (Canary yellow)	0.25 (0.25)	7.10 6.96	10.52 10.84	8.46 8.27
Al(OPr ⁱ) ₃ (0.52)	AcNaph.TSCZH (1.23)	1 : 2	240 (Dark yellow)	0.28 (0.28)	4.85 4.72	14.51 14.72	11.56 11.23
Al(OPr ⁱ) ₃ (0.32)	AcNaph.TSCZH (1.15)	1 : 3	180 Yellow	0.28 (0.26)	3.50 3.57	16.38 16.71	12.96 12.75

*Satisfactory C and H analyses were obtained.

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF t-BUTOXYALUMINIUM(III) COMPLEXES

Reactants			Decomp. temp. (°C)/ (Colour)	Analysis Pr ⁱ OH (g)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)*		
Al compd. (g)	Bu ⁱ OH (g)	Molar ratio			Al	N	S
Al(OPr ⁱ) (AcFur.TSCZ) ₂ (0.66)	0.11	1 : 1	270 (Light yellow)	0.09 (0.09)	5.65 5.80	17.68 18.09	14.13 13.80
Al(OPr ⁱ) (AcFur.TSCZ) ₂ (0.86)	0.39	1 : 2	240 (Yellow)	0.30 (0.31)	7.48 7.59	11.54 11.82	9.36 9.02
Al(OPr ⁱ) (AcThiop.TSCZ) ₂ (0.66)	0.10	1 : 1	105 (Yellow)	0.08 (0.08)	5.56 5.43	16.68 16.92	26.45 25.82
Al(OPr ⁱ) (AcThiop.TSCZ) ₂ (0.94)	0.40	1 : 2	130 (Yellow)	0.33 (0.33)	7.35 7.26	10.98 11.31	17.73 17.26
Al(OPr ⁱ) (AcPyd.TSCZ) ₂ (0.55)	0.08	1 : 1	180 (Light brown)	0.07 (0.07)	5.62 5.54	17.45 23.02	13.54 13.17
Al(OPr ⁱ) (AcPyd.TSCZ) ₂ (0.74)	0.32	1 : 2	290 (Yellow)	0.26 (0.26)	7.18 7.36	14.94 15.28	9.12 8.74
Al(OPr ⁱ) (AcNaph.TSCZ) ₂ (0.58)	0.07	1 : 1	264 (Dark yellow)	0.06 (0.06)	4.74 4.61	14.12 14.37	11.23 10.96
Al(OPr ⁱ) ₂ (AcNaph.TSCZ) ₂ (0.45)	0.17	1 : 2	230 (Canary yellow)	0.14 (0.14)	6.58 6.49	9.85 10.11	7.98 7.71

*Satisfactory C and H analyses were obtained.

Experimental

Thiosemicarbazones (Table 1) were prepared by condensing thiosemicarbazide with heterocyclic ketones, viz. 2-acetylfuran, 2-acetylthiophene, 2-acetylpyridine and 2-acetylnaphthalene in refluxing ethanol as reported earlier⁵.

Preparation of complexes : A benzene solution of the requisite amount of the ligand (0.73–1.28 g) was added to a benzene solution of the calculated amount of aluminium(III) isopropoxide (0.32–1.28 g). The resulting mixture was refluxed for 6–14 h. The completion of the reaction was confirmed by the amount of isopropanol liberated during the reaction as an azeotrope with benzene. The solvent was then removed and the residue was dried under reduced pressure at 60° for about 2 h to yield the products (Table 2). Similarly the exchange reactions of mono- and bis-isopropoxyaluminium(III) complexes by t-butanol were also carried out (Table 3).

Aluminium was estimated as oxinate and isopropanol by dichromate oxidation. Carbon and hydrogen analyses were carried out at the Micro-analytical Laboratory of the Department. Nitrogen was determined by the Kjeldahl's method and sulphur by Messenger's method. Molecular weights

were determined in benzene by ebullioscopic method. Ir spectra (nujol/KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra were recorded on a Jeol FX-90Q spectrometer in CDCl₃ and benzene using TMS as the internal standard.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (N.C.B.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial support.

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